

Multimodal Narrative Design, Literacy and Cross-modal Synthesis for Meaning-making of Complex Adaptive Microbial Systems

Towards a Blind and Visually Impaired Accessible Smart Microscopy

Gamze Gülez
gamgulez@gmail.com

Introduction

Studying microbial life is challenging. Not only is the microbial world a complex adaptive system, but it is also largely invisible to the naked eye. Despite advanced scientific knowledge, cutting-edge microscopes, instruments, and methods, we still only have a limited view of this world. Microbiology is also one of the least accessible fields for blind and visually impaired (BVI) individuals, as the same technologies that enable sighted people to access the microbial world rely heavily on visual observation and analysis, besides wet-lab navigation and safety challenges (Heard, 2023). Even the advances in machine learning-driven smart microscopy employing event-driven, quality-driven, outcome-driven, and even information-driven automation applied in diverse research (Hinderling et al., 2025; Volpe et al., 2026) do not change the current picture much when it comes to BVI accessibility. However, I think that future artificial intelligence (AI)-based smart microscopy has the potential to reduce and even eliminate the barriers to BVI individuals while also advancing our understanding of complex microbial systems, especially if our efforts go beyond developing a highly efficient automation tool and move towards developing a meaning-making collaborator, as suggested by Katherine Hayles in her book *Bacteria to AI* (2025).

So, how do we develop meaning-making smart microscopy, advance our understanding of complex microbial adaptive systems, and make microbiology accessible to BVI individuals? My answer to that is: through narrative synthesis (Figure 1). Indeed, in their recent paper, in “From Observation to Understanding: A Multi-agent Framework for Smart Microscopy”, Kesavan and Nordenfelt (2025) already proposed a general framework for a future smart microscopy that functions as a meaning-making collaborator. Among many elements of their framework, for the narrative synthesis they stated, “Perhaps the most noticeable gap in current automated microscopy is the lack of narrative synthesis, the ability to translate raw data and analytic results into a coherent explanation of what’s happening biologically.”

Here I propose a narrative synthesis framework where multimodal narrative design, literacy, and cross-modal synthesis are at the core (Figure 2). From this point on I refer to multimodal narrative design and literacy as comic design and comic literacy, respectively.

Comic Design and Literacy

When we construct a scientific narrative, we combine multimodal experimental results and analysis, such as from microscopy images, quantitative and qualitative data, and arrange them within the scope of our prior knowledge and anticipation. Similarly, comics, already a multimodal medium that combines visuals with text, construct narratives not only about what is illustrated and written in each panel but also about how they are arranged, sized, shaped, connected, and related to guide readers’ understanding and anticipation (McCloud, 2006).

It is not only how we design the comics that is motivating me to suggest a comic framework for narrative synthesis, but also how we read comics, which makes it very relevant to how the meaning is generated in AI. Comic reading is complex; it involves parallel processing of text and images as well as hierarchical and rhizomatic (interconnected network) processing of the narrative (Sousanis, 2015). The brain processes sequential images individually but also all images simultaneously, continuously relating, connecting, and filling in the gaps to anticipate what comes next. Given the advances in computer vision, text, and data processing, current AI-based systems are already offering multimodal processing capabilities. These features are valuable for training AI systems in narrative thinking to design and understand complex narratives, not just hierarchical but also rhizomatic relationships.

That is why I think comics are the most suitable medium for handling complex microbial systems. In Table 1, I summarized how comics can handle some of the key complexity elements in microbial systems. At this point, I invite curious readers to explore Nick Sousanis's *Unflattening* (2015), a thesis in comic format illustrating the power of comics in handling complexity, nonlinearity, interconnectedness, different ways of seeing, and meaning-making.

Table 1. Elements of Complexity in Microbial Systems and Comic Design

Elements of Complexity	Example in Microbial System	How can comics handle that?
Nonlinearity	Threshold responses such as quorum sensing.	Panels show separate moments of space and time, yet also everything at once. (Past-Present-Future) Panel bleeding Multithread entry (re-entrant processing) Panel size is about the speed of time and distance in space. Different designs, like spirals, from bottom to up, diagonal narratives, and connections Overlaid panels on the main panels can show different scales and directions simultaneously
Interconnectedness	Interaction between microorganisms such as via metabolic exchange	
Simultaneity and Spatiotemporality	Diffusion of metabolites and their effects can manifest at another location in the colony. An act of individual cell can have an immediate effect nearby and also further at a later time	
Feedback Loops	Glutamate stress-membrane potential modification, resulting in oscillations in bacterial colony growth	
Multiscalarity	Colony level changes vs individual cells, molecular level changes affecting behavior at the macro-level	
Multidimensionality	How colonies grow: 3-D structures	

Cross-modal Synthesis

When we read a comic or analyze scientific data, we form the meaning in our brain. When it comes time to disseminate, we translate our understanding into another modality such as text or speech so that others can access what we found or created. Such translations, however, can overlook important aspects and information. They are also usually not adequate for BVI accessibility as they may still refer to visuals and visual analogies. Hence, we need to create relatable and meaningful cross-modal synthesis. Naturally, feedback from BVI individuals at this stage is crucial to come up with meaningful syntheses. After we achieve this, we can train AI systems to generate cross-modal syntheses and implement them into smart microscopy. This smart microscopy, by synthesizing narratives in different modalities automatically, will then enable BVI individuals to access microscopy. Furthermore, given that other senses, such as hearing and

touch, of especially early-blinded individuals are enhanced due to heavy reliance on such senses (Fine and Park, 2018), syntheses in different modalities, such as sound, could offer new insights and discoveries that other people might miss.

Complex Systems and Stories of Calvino

Making meaning out of a microbiology experiment is similar to what the master of non-linear storytelling Italo Calvino did in his works, such as *Invisible Cities* (1972/2023) and *The Castle of Crossed Destinies* (1973/1998). In *Invisible Cities*, Calvino tells stories of fictional cities written as a conversation between Marco Polo and Kublai Khan. Polo synthesizes his understanding of the world, sharing it with Kublai Khan so that Kublai mentally reconstructs and understands that world. The microbial world is like invisible cities; we know some things about them, we discover some new things while we visit them through our experiments, instruments, yet we still don't know everything. While we navigate, we connect the known to the unknown, making that world visible by creating meaning via our narration in the complex architecture, terrain, interactions, and functions. Similar to the interaction between Marco Polo and Kublai Khan, BVI individuals, sighted individuals, and AI collaborators interact with each other to share their understanding of complex microbial systems and by changing the direction of interaction, they create more insights and perspectives. In *The Castle of Crossed Destinies*, Calvino tells intersecting stories by making the characters tell their stories with narrative cards. In my mind, the cards resemble to microscopy images and comics panels, arranged in multiple ways, giving rise to multiple, intersecting narratives.

Roadmap

Figure 3 shows the roadmap, where some paths can be walked in parallel to achieve meaning-making smart microscopy, or better call it “Multimodal Multisensory Narrative Synthesis Collaborator”. For the prototype of the cross-modal synthesis of a non-linear comic please check the appendix.

Final Words

While automation is necessary and important, I fear that we are solely focusing on hyper-efficiency, standardization, and perfection, turning AI technologies into hypothesis-generating crystal balls; fulfilling our worst fears of tools replacing humans. And even if the hypotheses would truly be useful, as Tan and Liu (2026) already pointed out, we don't have enough resources to pursue every hypothesis. Choosing the next hypothesis to follow itself would cause decision fatigue, which likely requires delegating it to another decision-making AI. This would create a nightmarish loop for the humans. However, if we approach AI as a meaning-making collaborator, we have a chance to coexist. After all, as Hayles (2025) already pointed out, we have already been shaped by techno-genesis, our tools shaping us and we shaping our tools, long before digital technologies. The difference now is that everything is happening and spreading too rapidly, so we need to cultivate some brakes and resist the temptation to take shortcuts. To avoid averaging responses from our AI collaborator, humans must always be in the loop. We should ask multiple narratives, challenge those narratives with our own narratives, and be challenged by the AI-generated narratives to shape each other for the better.

Note that my intention is not to create a comic-making AI. I prefer human-made comics and I prefer to make my own comics. For me, the process is important as much as the outcome; getting lost and finding my way by observing, combining, questioning, making multiple decisions, iterating are important elements of the process.

References

1. Hayles, N. K. (2025). *Bacteria to AI: Human futures with our nonhuman symbionts*. University of Chicago Press
2. Sousanis, N. (2015). *Unflattening*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
3. Heard, B. (2023) Supporting students with blindness and visual impairments in microbiology. *FEMS Microbiology Letters*, 2023, 370, 1–7 <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsle/fnad029>
4. Kesavan, P. S., & Nordenfelt, P. (2026). From observation to understanding: A multi-agent framework for smart microscopy. *Journal of*

Microscopy. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jmi.70063>

5. Hinderling, L., Heil, H. S., Rates, A. et al. (2025). Smart microscopy: Current implementations and a roadmap for interoperability [Preprint]. bioRxiv. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.08.18.670881>
6. Volpe, G., Wählby, C., Tian, L., et al. (2026). Roadmap on deep learning for microscopy. *Journal of Physics: Photonics*, 8(1), 012501. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7647/ae0fd1>
7. Tan, C. and Liu, H. (2026) The Mirage of Autonomous AI Scientists https://chenhaot.com/papers/mirage_ai_scientist.pdf
8. Fine I, Park JM. (2018) Blindness and Human Brain Plasticity. *Annu. Rev. Vis. Sci.* Vol.4:337-356. doi: 10.1146/annurev-vision-102016-061241. Epub 2018 Jul 5. PMID: 29975591.
9. McCloud, S. (2006). *Making Comics : Storytelling Secrets of Comics, Manga and Graphic Novels*. New York: Harper
10. Calvino, I. (2023). *Invisible cities* (W. Weaver, Trans.). Vintage Classics. (Original work published 1972)
11. Calvino, I. (1998). *The castle of crossed destinies* (W. Weaver, Trans.). Vintage Books. (Original work published 1973)

Appendix

The work below, shows a 2-page non-linear comic example as well as its cross-modal synthesis as a transcript. The audio-video version of the cross-modal synthesis and design process can be accessed at <https://gamzegulez.wixsite.com/gamzegulez/accessible-comic-1>

Figure A1. 2-page non-linear comic titled A Pedogenetic Resolution of Spacetime Paradox

Cross-modal Synthesis Transcript

The title of the comic is : A Pedogenetic resolution of spacetime paradox.

Pedogenesis is the scientific term for soil formation. It is a philosophical poetic comic about soil formation, longing for mountains and interconnectedness of life.

It is a 2 page comic. There are no dialogue, instead a poetic text to accompany the drawings in a few panels.

The drawings are simple, with a limited color palette, creating a calm, serene tone matching the poetic text.

Page 1

Page 1 has 3 main rectangular panels laid out into 3 rows. The first 2 panels are the same height, while the third with twice as high, covering the bottom half of the page.

Panel 1:

On the left is a mountain, colored in grey tones, like a cold stone. The first sentence begins near the mountain with the word “you” and continues into Panel 2 below. The words are separated by wide, empty spaces as if the text itself is traveling through space and time depicted by vast sky.

Panel 2:

At the right end of the pane is the face of a woman. Her hair is wavy as if moving gently in the air, It is colored in soft orange, like the taste of a mild chilly pepper and a cold soft peach mixture. Some of her hair is drawn out of the panel frame, hinting at a sense of freedom.

Her head is slightly tilted up, her eyes gazing towards the mountain on the left, as if she is looking at the mountain with her mind and heart.

The text reads: and I are so far away now

This stresses the distance between the mountain and the woman.

Panel 3:

This panel covers the bottom half of the page and contains 2 overlaid panels. At the right edge, the woman is shown from her side view, nude and kneeling. Her arms extend toward the soil. Her hands are shown closer, from the top via a small, square overlaid panel; they are holding soil, which has the color like the warmth of cinnamon and ginger drink.

A larger rectangular overlaid panel at the top shows a mountain range. Right beside the panel is a text with words pulled closer together, suggesting that as the woman connects with the soil, the distance in spacetime collapses.

The text reads:

Yet, still so
Close
We are

And continues below the larger overlaid panel, to the left of the woman's hand:

As your past
Is present
In the hand of
Your future

Page 2

There are 5 main panels laid-out in 4 rows, all of similar height. First row contains panel 1 and panel 2. There are also multiple smaller panels overlaid on the main panels and the gaps between them, acting as snapshots through space and time to show movement and transformation.

Panel 1:

The same stone cold grey mountain from page 1 stands at the left edge of this panel. 8 small overlaid panels being here and pass through panels 3, 4 and 5 showing a large rock piece falling from the mountain and being transported by a stream.

Panel 2:

The stream flows diagonally from the right side of the page to the left, starting in middle of the mountain range and ending at the upper corner of the final panel. The blue tones of the stream suggest a vibrant yet also cold, high energy movement, like someone rolling down a snow-covered hill with joyful screams. As it flows, the stream widens because it is closer to the woman.

Panel 3 and 4:

Rock pieces are distributed around the stream against a background of soft, warm grey stone.

In Panel 3, the text reads:

Is this Shiva's Divine dance
Gaia's biogeochemical wisdom

Overlaid Panels: The bottom of Panel 4 and top of Panel 5 are overlaid with four smaller panels. First one is the final snapshot of the rock that fell from the mountain, seen closely with lichens on top. The lichens are colored in orange, like the taste of a warm, citrusy and spicy orange tea.

The other three panels depict the transformation: cracks made by lichen acidity and weathering from rain gradually erode the rock. The resulting soil is initially a dark brown—like the taste of dark chocolate—with small plants and rock fragments, eventually turning an orange-brown, as if ginger and cinnamon were ground together, smaller and softer to touch. Smaller red images, representing the high energy of fire, depict microbial activity and the resulting fertility of the ecosystem.

Panel 5:

The whole panel is covered in warm ginger-and-cinnamon-colored soil. In the right corner, the woman's bare feet are seen from above. Her toenails are painted green, like the sensation of touching and smelling fresh grass.

The final text on the left reads:

Or Pan Gu's decomposing corpse
That I am standing on,
Occupying all times
At this space once.